

Truth vs Reality: From Sexsomnia to Schizophrenia and from Schizophrenia to Awakening

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Abstract

This case study explores the intersection between altered states of consciousness and mental health deterioration, focusing on a young father who unknowingly fathers a child due to a sexsomnia episode. His partner conceals the child's existence, triggering a series of psychotic symptoms resembling schizophrenia in the father. Inspired by the myth of Athena's birth from Zeus—where Zeus is unaware of Metis's pregnancy—the study analyzes how hidden truths affect the individual's perception of reality and lead to psychological disintegration. The father's eventual uncovering of the truth allows him to reconnect with reality, resolving his psychosis and demonstrating the therapeutic potential of uncovering concealed truths in mental health.

Summary

This case examines the psychological journey of a young man who, due to an incident of sexsomnia—a state where individuals perform sexual acts while asleep—fathered a child without his awareness. The young mother, driven by various factors, chose to conceal the pregnancy and birth, mirroring the myth of Athena's birth from Zeus, who was unaware of Metis's pregnancy. Over time, this lack of awareness and the absence of truth caused the father to lose touch with reality, culminating in psychotic symptoms that mimicked schizophrenia. As he gradually uncovered the concealed truth, he re-established his connection to reality, causing the psychotic symptoms to subside, thus reasserting the critical role of truth in mental health stability.

Method

This study uses a qualitative approach, analyzing the psychological impact of concealed truths on mental health, focusing on cases involving altered states of consciousness, such as sexsomnia, and resulting psychiatric symptoms. The data includes a detailed case history of the patient, observational reports, and psychological assessments to evaluate the onset and

remission of psychotic symptoms over time. Additionally, mythological analysis is used as a symbolic framework to understand the archetypal elements in the case. This symbolic layer allows for a deeper exploration of how concealed truths affect an individual's internal and external reality.

Discussion

This case illustrates how concealed truths can drive individuals into a distorted perception of reality, potentially leading to severe mental health issues such as psychosis or schizophrenia. The young father's experience parallels the myth of Athena's birth, where Zeus's lack of awareness regarding Metis's pregnancy causes a split between personal truth and social reality. In this case, the young father's psychotic symptoms can be interpreted as the result of a similar concealment, where the hidden truth regarding his child creates a fractured self-concept. This situation aligns with theories suggesting that when a person's truth is manipulated or withheld by their social environment, it can lead to disorientation, alienation, and mental fragmentation.

Additionally, the case raises questions regarding the impact of altered states of consciousness, such as those seen in *sexsomnia*, which challenge traditional understandings of accountability and awareness. In this case, the inability of the young man to recall or integrate his actions into his conscious reality results in profound personal consequences. The psychological symptoms observed in this case suggest that mental health outcomes may be significantly affected by the way individuals reconstruct their reality based on what is disclosed or hidden by others around them.

Conclusions

The resolution of the young man's psychotic symptoms upon discovering the truth highlights the therapeutic potential of uncovering concealed realities in treating certain mental health conditions. This case underscores that when individuals reconnect with their "hidden truths"—even those initially concealed by altered states of consciousness or other psychological factors—there is an opportunity for mental and emotional healing. Consequently, therapeutic approaches that prioritize the revelation of significant concealed aspects in a patient's life may prove beneficial, especially in cases where reality distortion has contributed to mental health deterioration.